

Fig. S2. Efficiency and toxicity of C11 molecule dissolved in water. (A) The antivirulence efficacy of C11 was tested with embryos injured in the tail fin and bath infected with PAO1 suspension at approximately 7×10^7 CFU/mL in presence of C11 dissolved in H₂O at 25 µM. A significant difference ($***P < 0.001$) is found in the survival curve of C11 treated embryos comparatively to non treated embryos. **(B)** The toxicity of C11 at 25 µM (dissolved in H₂O) was monitored after immersion of embryos injured in the tail fin. For all experiments, the embryo survival was monitored for 45 hours and survival curves were represented with a Kaplan-Meier representation. Graphs represent the pool of three independent experiments (n = 60 larvae in total per condition).